

United States Department of the Interior

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In reply refer to:
2023-0126888-S7-001

July 15, 2024

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Subject: Formal Conference and Consultation on the Martinez Dock Repair Project (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: SPN-2009-00386) and Appending to the December 1, 2004, Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on the Delta Smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and its Critical Habitat (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service File Number: 1-1-04-F-0345)

Dear Ms. Malamud-Roam:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) December 22, 2023, letter requesting formal conference and consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Martinez Dock Repair Project (proposed project) within the Carquinez Strait in City of Martinez, Contra Costa County, California. The Corps determined the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the federally threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and the federally proposed as endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta distinct population segment (DPS) of the longfin smelt (*Spirinchus thaleichthys*). Critical habitat for the longfin smelt has not yet been proposed. The Corps also determined the proposed project may affect but is not likely to adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) and designated critical habitat for the delta smelt. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

The Federal action on which we are conferencing and consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*, and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*, for the replacement or repair of 59 existing timber piles, bracing and decking related to maintenance of Martinez Refining Company, LLC's Martinez Marine Terminal.

In reviewing this proposed project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' December 22, 2023, letter with enclosures including a biological assessment dated October 2023; (2) a revised biological assessment dated May 2024; and (3) other information available to the Service.

Delta Smelt Critical Habitat

The Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the proposed project may affect but is not likely to adversely affect designated critical habitat for the delta smelt. The proposed project is proposing to replace the existing structural supports within the same footprint, so no loss of habitat is anticipated. The project is not expected to permanently affect any of the primary constituent elements of the designated critical habitat. Implementation of the *Conservation Measures* below will minimize the risk of contaminants entering the river further reducing the potential for the proposed project to adversely affect critical habitat.

California Ridgway's Rail and Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Service does not concur with the Corps' not likely to adversely affect determination for the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and has prepared the biological opinion below. Suitable habitat is present for both species in the Action Area where the wharf approach trestle meets the tidal marsh and extends southward. A 2008 California Natural Diversity Database record of California Ridgway rail was identified 900 feet east of the wharf approach trestle but recent surveys have not been conducted. These species within this habitat may be subject to consequences from disturbance during construction and pile driving.

Programmatic Biological Opinion Applicability

After review of the proposed project, the Service has determined that the proposed project meets the suitability criteria and is within the geographic area analyzed in the Service's December 1, 2004, *Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on the Delta Smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and its Critical Habitat* (Programmatic Biological Opinion). A copy of the Programmatic Biological Opinion is available on the Corps website: https://www.spk.usace.army.mil/Portals/12/documents/regulatory/pdf/Programmatic%20Biological%20Opinions/2004.12.01_coe_delta_sme lt.pdf. This letter is an agreement by the Service to append the proposed project to the Programmatic Biological Opinion and represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed action for the delta smelt.

The remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California Ridgway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, delta smelt, and conference opinion on the effects of the proposed project for the longfin smelt.

Consultation History

December 22, 2023	The Service received the Corps request for formal conference and consultation.
February 29, 2024	The Service emailed the Corps with requests for clarification and an updated habitat assessment.
May 31, 2024	The Service received a revised biological assessment.
June 20, 2024	The Service and Corps exchanged emails regarding the revised biological assessment and species determinations.

BIOLOGICAL and CONFERENCE OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Martinez Refining Company, LLC (MRC) is proposing repairs at its marine oil terminal wharf approach trestle in Martinez, California. The proposed project would replace forty (40) trestle piles, install three (3) pile jackets, and remove and replace eight (8) timber members. Construction activities will occur along the length of the MRC wharf approach trestle and materials will be brought in by marine barge for the parts of the repair work located in deep enough water for barge access. No work will occur in the terrestrial environment with the exception of access along existing roads as needed. No entry into naturally vegetated areas is proposed. Work will be completed in-water with a spud barge (spuds used to maintain position), work skiffs, and crane barge. The work is scheduled to commence in 2024 and is estimated to take 10 weeks in total to complete, with in-water work scheduled to occur between August and November. Construction will take place during daylight hours only.

Pile Replacements

MRC has proposed in kind replacement with new treated and coated timber piles. Existing piles will be cut off at least three feet below the mudline. Ammoniacal Copper Zinc Arsenate (ACZA) will be used to treat the piles and the top 50 feet of the piles will be coated with PPG Amerlock 2, a two-part high epoxy coating, and sealed with Amerlock Sealer to prevent leaching of ACZA into the water. A diesel impact hammer with swinging leads will drive the piles to grade or to refusal. The piles will then be pulled under existing timber caps and fastened with hot-dipped galvanized hardware.

Pile Jacket Installation

Three piles cannot be replaced due to construction interferences. These piles will be repaired by installation of fiberglass sleeves filled with grout. The grout will be tremied into the sleeve from a portable grouting station. The sleeves will be installed by divers due to the location of the piles and the size of the sleeves.

Removal and Replacement of Timber Members

Four 6-inch by 12-inch timber sisters, one 12-inch by 12-inch timber cap, two 4-inch by 12-inch timber roadway stringers, and one pile cap connection require in kind replacement. ACZA will be used to treat new timber members. The timber members will be coated with PPG Amerlock 2 and sealed with Amerlock Sealer to prevent leaching of ACZA into the water. The existing timber members will be removed with hand tools, lifted from the trestle by a derrick barge, and placed on a material barge for disposal. The new members will be fastened into place with new hot-dipped galvanized hardware using hand tools. Work will be completed from boats and floats.

Conservation Measures

In addition to the *Conservation Measures* in the Programmatic Biological Opinion, MRC proposes the following *Conservation Measures*:

1. Where above water work is being performed, tarps and other similar devices will be used to capture any debris loosened by the work. In addition, if any debris should fall into the water, it will be expeditiously removed to the extent practicable.
2. Debris and other materials removed will be disposed of in accordance with Federal, State, and local requirements.
3. All construction personnel will receive environmental awareness training from a qualified biologist before commencing work on the Action. The training will be prepared by a biologist familiar with the species of concern that may be present at or near the proposed project, and will cover listed species that may be present, environmental laws and protections, and permit conditions.
4. To minimize impacts to migrating fish, all in-water construction shall be conducted within the established environmental work window between June 1 and November 30 (the Service assumes this is a National Marine Fisheries Service work window), designed to avoid potential impacts to fish species. If possible, a soft start technique be implemented to allow any potentially impacted species to vacate the Action Area. (Please note, the Programmatic Biological Opinion requires the Corps to restrict in-water work to August 1 through November 30 in the Central Zone).
5. To minimize impacts to potentially present California Ridgway's rail, pile replacement work within 175 feet of tidal marsh habitat will occur outside of the February 1 through August 31 nesting season for the California Ridgway's rail.

Protocol-level surveys shall be conducted if areas within or adjacent to rail habitat and nesting locations cannot be avoided during the breeding season (February 1 through August 31). The surveys will focus on potential habitat that could be disturbed by construction activities during the breeding season to ensure that rails are not breeding in these locations. (Please note the timing, Service approval, and permit requirements of

protocol-level surveys).

If breeding California Ridgway's rails or California black rails (*Laterallus jamaicensis coturniculus*) are not detected during surveys, or if their breeding territories can be avoided by 500 feet (150 meters), then the proposed project activities may proceed at that location.

If protocol surveys determine that breeding California Ridgway's rails or black rails are present in the proposed project area, the following measures would apply to the proposed project activities conducted during their breeding season (February 1 through August 31):

- An approved biologist with experience recognizing California Ridgway's rail and black rail vocalizations will be on site during construction activities occurring within 500 feet (150 meters) of suitable rail breeding habitat.
6. To avoid impacts to potentially present salt marsh harvest mouse, construction activities within 175 feet of suitable habitat will be scheduled to avoid extreme high tides when there is potential for salt marsh harvest mouse to move to higher, drier grounds, such as ruderal and grassland habitats. Extreme high tides would be in excess of six feet as predicted for the nearest tide gauge, Point Chicago tide gauge.
 7. No equipment staging, access, or work activities shall be conducted within natural terrestrial habitat along the shoreline.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action." The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, lighting, or movement associated with the proposed project. Therefore, the Action Area includes the trestle structure and approximately 330 feet on either side of the trestle to account for hydroacoustic and terrestrial visual and noise effects. The Service estimates this overall area to be approximately 16 acres.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

"Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species.

It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed Action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

Delta Smelt

The status of the species has been updated since the issuance of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Please refer to the 2022 delta smelt Species Assessment and Listing Priority Assignment Form of the Candidate Notice of Review for the status of the species. Electronic copies of this document are available at https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/publication/4119.pdf (Service 2023).

In December 2021, the Service, along with the California Department of Fish and Wildlife, California Department of Water Resources, and U.S. Bureau of Reclamation, began experimentally releasing captively produced delta smelt into the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta in an experiment intended to help inform future supplementation of the species in the wild.

Experimental release of captively produced, marked delta smelt continued for a third year from November 2023 through January 2024. During this third year a total of 91,468 delta smelt were released over 6 release periods in the Sacramento River at Rio Vista. A small subsample of those marked fish have also been recaptured.

Longfin Smelt

The Service proposed to list the San Francisco Bay-Delta DPS of the longfin smelt as endangered on October 7, 2022 (Service 2022a). For the comprehensive assessment of the longfin smelt DPS, please refer to the proposed listing at <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2022-10-07/pdf/2022-21605.pdf> and the Species Status Assessment for the San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of the Longfin Smelt at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ServCat/DownloadFile/223002> (Service 2022b).

California Ridgway's Rail

The status of California Ridgway's rail and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California (Service 2013). This document can be found at:

https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf.

It is identified by its previous name as the California clapper rail in this Recovery Plan as the species' common and scientific name was recently revised to reflect the currently accepted taxonomy and nomenclature (Service 2023). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at:

https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal Projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The proposed project is located in the open water and nearshore shallow waters of the Carquinez Strait and consists of the existing MRC wharf approach trestle. The trestle extends from the shoreline of the City of Martinez into the Carquinez Strait and is approximately 2,800 feet west of the Benicia-Martinez Bridge and south of the Port of Benicia.

Land use in the vicinity of the MRC wharf approach trestle is a mix of industrial and open space. Habitats within the Action Area include nearshore estuarine/marsh habitat, mudflats, coastal scrub, open water, and developed infrastructure. Coastal brackish marsh is present along the shoreline between Bulls Head Point (also known as Suisun Point) to the east and the Martinez Marina to the west of the approach trestle, including the shoreline area directly adjacent to the

trestle. The nearshore estuarine/marsh habitat was dominated by cattail (*Typha* sp.), common reed (*Phragmites australis*), tules (*Scirpus* spp.), and California bulrush (*Schoenoplectus Californicus*). Common reed and cattail were observed to be the co-dominant vegetation with tule and bulrush also being abundant. Pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*), salt grass (*Distichlis spicata*), and marsh jaumea (*Jaumea carnosa*) were only observed in the transition zone between tidal brackish marsh and the coastal scrub habitat. However, based on limitations of the survey for the revised biological assessment, the presence of these species cannot be ruled out within the Action Area. These plant species suggest the near-marsh habitat is tidal brackish with seasonal freshwater influences.

Open water habitat within the Action Area consists of the estuarine waters of the Carquinez Strait, which support numerous native and nonnative fish species. The developed infrastructure includes the MRC wharf approach trestle, which provides shade and refuge areas for predatory fish and resting spots and foraging and predatory opportunities for fish, birds, and marine mammals. Existing support piles provide attachment areas for sessile invertebrates.

Numerous consultations have occurred within the Action Area. The most recent biological opinion was issued on October 15, 2015 for the amendment to the initial May 22, 2014 biological opinion on the seismic strengthening of the trestle structure (Service File Numbers: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0054 and 08FBDT00-2013-F-0054-R001). Additional informal consultations at this site were issued on June 29, 2011 for work over the brackish marsh section of the trestle (Service File Number: 81420-2011-I-0561-1) and on March 23, 2012 for fender replacement (Service File Number: 08ESMF00-2012-I-0173).

Delta Smelt

The Carquinez Strait is a narrow gap in the Coast Range that connects San Pablo Bay with Suisun Bay. Delta smelt are known to occur in Carquinez Strait and may occur in the open waters within and adjacent to the Action Area throughout the year if habitat conditions warrant. Delta smelt are less likely to occur in the Action Area during Programmatic Biological Opinion in-water work window of August 1 through November 30 but may occur if the low salinity zone remains in Suisun Bay just east of the Carquinez Strait. Delta smelt are less likely to be in the Action Area if the low salinity zone is further upstream. Delta smelt abundance is historically low and continues to trend downward with the exception of the broodstock experimentally released fish.

Longfin Smelt

Longfin smelt are known to occur in the Carquinez Strait and may occur in the open waters within and adjacent to the Action Area throughout the year if habitat conditions warrant. The longfin smelt DPS relative abundance is low and the species has been proposed by the Service to be listed as endangered.

California Ridgway's Rail and Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Potentially marginal suitable habitat is present where the wharf approach trestle meets the tidal

marsh. Based on the May 2024 site visit for the revised biological assessment, the adjacent marsh is characterized by species typically associated with tidal brackish marsh. The near-shore marsh does not contain the vegetation species normally associated with California Ridgway's rail habitat as described above. The upper marsh does contain pickleweed and gumplant (*Grindelia camporum*), both preferred plant species. Per the biological assessment, a 2008 record of California Ridgway's rail was identified 900 feet east of the wharf approach trestle. Recent surveys have not been conducted within the vicinity of the proposed project. The habitat within the Action Area and contiguous areas contain varied suitability but it is reasonable to assume California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice utilize the Action Area and would be subject to effects from construction.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Delta Smelt

The proposed project is not expected to result in any additional effects not already analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The proposed repairs will have an adverse effect on delta smelt if individuals are present and are temporarily deterred from utilizing the aquatic environment due to physical (increased turbidity and suspended sediments) and noise/vibration disturbances from pile removal that interfere with normal behaviors. Avoidance of the Action Area by the delta smelt or deterrence from traversing through the channel during construction could also expose the delta smelt to predation that would not have occurred otherwise. However, delta smelt are less likely to be present in the Action Area during the August 1 to November 30 work window for the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The construction effects to delta smelt are reduced by conducting the proposed project during the Service's recommended work-window and incorporation of *Conservation Measures* consistent with the guidelines of the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

Longfin Smelt

Hydroacoustics

Longfin smelt may be affected by construction noise. Underwater sound pressure waves can harass and harm fish species (Hastings and Popper 2005; California Department of Transportation 2001). As the pressure wave passes through a fish, the swim bladder is rapidly squeezed due to the high pressure, and then rapidly expanded as the under-pressure component of the wave passes through the fish. This can cause adverse effects including rupture of the swim bladder, rupture of capillaries, internal hemorrhage, neurological stress, and auditory damage. Extreme sound waves can cause instantaneous death, latent death within minutes after exposure, or can occur several days later.

Elevated noise levels can cause sub-lethal injuries affecting survival and fitness. Similarly, if injury does not occur, noise may modify fish behavior that may make them more susceptible to predation. Fish suffering damage to hearing organs may suffer equilibrium problems and may have a reduced ability to detect predators and prey. Other types of sub-lethal injuries can place the fish at increased risk of predation and disease. Adverse effects on survival and fitness can occur even in the absence of overt injury. Exposure to elevated noise levels can cause a temporary shift in hearing sensitivity (referred to as a temporary threshold shift or TTS), decreasing sensory capability for periods lasting from hours to days (Hastings and Popper 2005; Popper and Hastings 2009; Hastings *et al.* 1996).

Turbidity and Contaminants

Construction activities would result in disturbances that are likely to temporarily increase turbidity and suspended sediment within the Action Area. Although longfin smelt are adapted to living in turbid environments, localized increases could adversely affect individual longfin smelt that may be present. Effects of increased turbidity and suspended sediment may temporarily degrade water quality, reduce prey resources, disturb habitat, and impede movements of longfin smelt. Spills or other chemical contamination from construction equipment could also negatively affect habitat and re-suspended sediments can sometimes elevate toxic levels in water. Implementation of the *Conservation Measures* would minimize but not eliminate the potential for these adverse effects to occur.

Habitat

The proposed project will result in the temporary loss of habitat within the Action Area due to increased activity, noise/vibration, and turbidity/suspended sediment. However, there will not be any permanent loss of habitat from the proposed activities.

California Ridgway's Rail and Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Proposed project activities will not occur within suitable habitat. However, construction noise and visual disturbance from construction activities pile driving close to habitat will result in adverse effects to California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice with the suitable brackish tidal marsh within the Action Area.

The biological assessment provided a summarized noise analysis that reported rails and mice within 138.71 feet and 174.61 feet, respectively, of pile driving would exhibit startle responses. According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 A-weighted decibels (dBA) above background levels can result in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance. In a study by Rasmussen *et al.* (2009), lab mice exposed to construction noise levels 70-90 dBA above background levels for ≥ 1 hour/day during gestation led to decreased reproductive efficiency (by decreasing live birth rates and increasing the number of stillborn pups). The Transportation Noise Control Center (1997) found that noise levels over 80 dBA above background levels caused behavior disruption in foraging, breeding, egg incubation, and rearing of young in various bird species. Individuals may also be subject to

higher levels of stress or predation due to the noise and masking effects of the noise. The implementation proposed *Conservation Measures* may reduce the impact of these effects.

For California Ridgway's rails, conducting work outside of the breeding season minimizes effects to breeding rails, their eggs, and young but it does not minimize disturbance to rails that may be present within the Action Area outside of the breeding season and may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual rails to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. With the language provided in the biological assessment and reiterated in the *Description of the Proposed Action*, the proposed project may occur during the breeding season and nest abandonment and predation could also occur.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

The Martinez Dock Repair Project as described, fits within the parameters of the level of effects analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion and is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the delta smelt.

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* of the longfin smelt, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action* and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's conference opinion that the Martinez Dock Repair Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the proposed longfin smelt DPS. This conclusion is based primarily on: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual longfin smelt, and (2) the project will only result in temporary effects to habitat for the longfin smelt DPS.

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for the California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Martinez Dock Repair Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California Ridgway's rail or the salt marsh harvest mouse. This conclusion is based primarily on: (1) the duration of construction noise will be temporary and limited to approximately 10 weeks; (2) the extent of noise impacts is small in scope to a localized area; and (3) suitable habitat large enough to support the species will not be physically disturbed.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of “take” in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(4)].

The prohibitions against taking the longfin smelt found in section 9 of the Act do not apply until the species is listed. However, the Service advises the Corps to consider implementing the following reasonable and prudent measures. If this conference opinion is adopted as a biological opinion following a listing, these measures, with their implementing terms and conditions, will be non-discretionary.

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates that juvenile and adult delta smelt and longfin smelt will be subject to take in the form of harm from interference of normal behaviors within the Action Area; therefore, the Service anticipates take in the form of harm of all delta smelt and longfin smelt within the approximately 16-acre Action Area. However, due to the timing and duration of the proposed project, the Service anticipates take of individuals will be minimized. Upon implementation of the Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service anticipates incidental take of the California Ridgway’s rail and salt marsh harvest mouse will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through dense vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, including injury or mortality from nest abandonment or increased stress and predation, and impairing the essential behaviors of all salt marsh harvest

mice and California Ridgway's rails within the contiguous brackish marsh within the 16-acre Action Area adjacent to the trestle. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of California Ridgway's rails and salt marsh harvest mice associated with the Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the delta smelt, longfin smelt, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The Service has determined that the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project on the species:

1. Adverse effects to delta smelt, longfin smelt, California Ridgway's rail, and salt marsh harvest mouse shall be minimized to the full extent possible.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implements the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. The project proponent shall fully implement the proposed project, including the Conservation Measures, guidelines, implementing procedure, the Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and the corresponding Terms and Conditions as described in this biological opinion and the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.

3. Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for the delta smelt, longfin smelt, California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation and conference on the Martinez Dock Repair Project. You may ask the Service to confirm the conference opinion as a biological opinion issued through formal consultation if the longfin smelt is listed. The request must be in writing via email or physical letter.

If the Service reviews the proposed action and finds that there have been no significant changes in the action as planned or in the information used during the conference, the Service will confirm the conference opinion as the biological opinion on the proposed project and no further section 7 consultation will be necessary.

As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

- (a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- (b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

The incidental take statement provided in this conference opinion does not become effective until the longfin smelt is listed and the conference opinion is adopted as the biological opinion issued through formal consultation. At that time, the project will be reviewed to determine whether any take of the longfin smelt has occurred. Modifications of the opinion and incidental take statement may be appropriate to reflect that take. No take of the longfin smelt may occur between the listing of species and the adoption of the conference opinion through formal consultation, or the completion of a subsequent formal consultation.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 2023-0126888-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this consultation.

Sincerely,

Heather Swinney
Acting Field Supervisor

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